

3. A. R. SELMER-OLSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1966, 20, 1621.
4. R. PRIBIL and V. VESELY, *Talanta*, 1970, 17, 801.
5. T. SUZUKI, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1966, 14, 420.
6. SH. A. SHERIF, A. S. ABDEL-GAWAD and A. M. EL-WAKIL, *Talanta*, 1970, 17, 137.
7. M. M. L. KHOSALA and S. P. RAO, *Talanta*, 1974, 21, 411.
8. A. M. KAPLUNOVA, N. I. ERSHOVA and T. A. BOLSHOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1978, 33, 1940.
9. J. P. BURNETTE, M. L. ARAUJO-BARREIRA, M. THAERI and M. J. F. LERROY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 73.
10. R. RAGHUNADHA RAO and S. M. KHOPKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 620.
11. M. B. CHAVAN and V. M. SHINDE, *Anal. Chim Acta*, 1972, 59, 165.
12. M. B. CHAVAN and V. M. SHINDE, *Sepp. Sci.*, 1973, 8, 285.
13. M. B. CHAVAN and V. M. SHINDE, *Chem Anal.*, 1974, 19, 1183.
14. Z. G. GARDLUND, R. J. CURTIS and G. W. SMITH, *Liq. Crystals Ordered Fluids*, 1973, 2, 541.
15. L. S. WOODWARD and A. A. NORD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3721.
16. K. A. KRAUS, F. NELSON and G. W. SMITH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 11.

Extraction of Palladium(II) with the Liquid Cation-exchanger Versatic 10

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SOLUTIONS of versatic acids in organic solvents behave as liquid cation-exchangers, the exchange properties of which are similar to those of organic ion-exchange resins. They have been used in our laboratory for the extraction of di-, tri-, and tetra-valent metals^{1,2}. However, no systematic attempt has yet been made to study the extraction behaviour of palladium(II) with versatic acids³. In this communication a rapid method for the extraction of milligram amounts of palladium(II) with the liquid cation-exchanger, Versatic 10 in benzene has been proposed.

Experimental

Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurement.

Versatic 10, a mixture of C₁₀ isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acids, had the concentration and the purity of 5.2 M and 99%, respectively⁴. It was standardised by the usual acid-alkalimetric titration. Solutions of Versatic 10 were prepared in benzene. Versatic 911, a mixture of saturated tertiary C₉, C₁₀ and C₁₁ monocarboxylic acids⁴, and SRS 100 (equiv. wt. 260–290), a high molecular weight synthetic carboxylic acid, supplied by Shell Chemical, were used without further purification. Palladium(II) solution (4.8 mg ml⁻¹) was

prepared by digesting PdCl₂ (Ranbaxy) (0.85 g) with 2 N HCl (20 ml) and then diluted to 100 ml. The solution was standardised by the complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) by a back-titration procedure with standard 0.01 M Th(NO₃)₄ using xylenol orange indicator⁵.

Extraction procedure: The aqueous phase contained 4.8 mg of palladium(II) in 0.1 M sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 6. pH was further adjusted when required by dilute sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 20 ml bringing the ultimate concentration of palladium in the aqueous phase to 2.4 × 10⁻³ M. The solution was equilibrated with 0.834 M Versatic 10 in benzene (1 : 6, 10 ml) for 10 min by manual shaking. Settling time was 10 min. The organic phase was stripped with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml) for 1 h by a mechanical shaker. After equilibration, the phases were settled (5 min) and the aqueous phase was separated. The amount of palladium was estimated from the acid extract complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of palladium(II) with Versatic 10 was performed at various pH at constant acetate (0.1 M) and extractant concentrations. Extraction of palladium increases with increased pH and becomes quantitative at pH 5.75. The distribution ratio (*D*) and the percentage of extraction of palladium(II) at different pH are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Versatic 10—Benzene (1 : 6)		Versatic 10—n-Hexane (1 : 6)	
	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %	Distribution ratio (<i>D_{Pd}</i>)	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %	Distribution ratio (<i>D_{Pd}</i>)
3.5	2.4	0.05	0.5	0.01
4.0	2.8	0.05	35.7	1.1
4.5	42.8	1.5	57.6	2.7
4.75	48.1	1.8	75.2	6.2
5.0	61.9	3.2	86.7	13.0
5.25	76.2	6.4	95.2	39.6
5.5	97.6	81.3	97.8	88.9
5.75	99.6	498	97.8	88.9

The effect of extractant on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of Versatic 10 from 0.026 to 0.834 M. A plot of log *D* vs log [Versatic 10] gives a straight line of slope 0.9. Shibata and Nishimura⁶ showed that Versatic 10 in organic diluent exists as a dimer (R₂H₂). The extraction mechanism of palladium(II) can therefore be proposed as

Among the diluents tested with Versatic quantitative extraction was achieved only in case of benzene

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF DILUENTS ON EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} WITH VERSATIC 10

Diluent	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %
Benzene	99.6
n-Hexane	97.8
Carbon tetrachloride	97.7
Chloroform	90.8
Xylene	91.3
Butanol	Emulsion
Toluene	72.6

(Table 2). Extraction behaviour of palladium(II) with Versatic 911 and SRS 100 has also been investigated. It was observed that the extraction of palladium(II) in case of SRS 100 was less than that of Versatic 911 (Table 3).

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE EXTRACTION BEHAVIOUR OF Pd^{II} WITH DIFFERENT CARBOXYLIC ACID IN BENZENE DILUENT (1 : 6)

pH	Versatic 911 Extraction %	SRS 100 Extraction %
3.5	15.3	41
4.0	29.8	64.1
4.5	67.9	72.6
4.75	87.2	89.3
5.00	95.7	93.6
5.25	100	94.4
5.5	100	94.8
5.75	100	95.3

Extractive separation : Palladium(II) was separated from several binary mixtures using the recommended extraction conditions. Mg, Ca, Ba and Sr did not interfere. Interference of Co, Ni, Mn, Zn and Cd was removed by using selected stripping

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} WITH VERSATIC 10

(Palladium = 4.8 mg, Foreign Ions = 5 mg, pH = 5.75)

Ion	Pd extracted %	Selective stripping agent
Mg ^{II}	99.8	
Ca ^{II}	99.8	
Ba ^{II}	99.7	
Sr ^{II}	99.7	
Fe ^{III} *	100.2	
Co ^{II}	99.2	1 N H ₂ SO ₄
Ni ^{II}	99.6	1 N H ₂ SO ₄
Mn ^{II}	99.6	1 N HCl
Zn ^{II}	99.4	0.5 N HCl
Cd ^{II}	99.4	1 N HCl
Al ^{III} *	98.0	
Th ^{IV} *	99.0	

*NaF used as masking agent.

agent, and interference of Al, Fe and Th by using NaF as masking agent (Table 4). Most of the platinum metals however interfere.

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References

1. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1981, 16, 87.
2. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 38.
3. A. W. ASHBROOK, *Miner. Sci. Eng.*, 1973, 5.
4. A. W. ASHBROOK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1721.
5. R. PRIBIL, "Chelometry-basic Determinations", Chempol, Prague, 1961.
6. J. SHIBATA and S. NISHIMURA, *Nippon Kinzoku Gakkaigishi*, 1975, 39, 206, 767.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Indium(III) with 1-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol

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THIAZOLYLAZO dyes give¹ sensitive methods for spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions in polar or non-polar phase. The complex formed between indium(III) and 2-(4-methyl-2-thiazolylazo)-5-ethylamino-*p*-cresol² requires extraction into chloroform. Maximum colour development takes place after 15 min in the reaction with 4-(2-thiazolylazo)resorcinol^{3,4}, and many ions are also found to interfere. The reaction of indium(III) with 5-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid⁵ and 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid⁶ has resulted in useful methods for its determination in polar phase. Since 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN) has been found¹ to be a sensitive chromogenic reagent, the reaction between indium(III) and TAN has been studied.

Experimental

Apparatus employed were the same as described earlier⁷. Stock solution indium(III), prepared by dissolving of indium sulphate pentahydrate (Fluka) (3.308 g) in 1% sulphuric acid (250 ml), was standardised complexometrically. A 0.1% (w/v) solution of TAN (Fluka) was prepared in methanol. Buffer solution of pH 3.5 was prepared from 0.05 M solutions of acetic acid and sodium hydroxide (B.D.H.). All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.